

Reporting wrongdoing related to software

This survey was designed at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and takes 10 minutes to complete. It is intended for anyone who is currently working as an IT professional (for example, software engineer, software tester, product owner, software consultant, data scientist, or CS researcher).

The purpose of this study is to assess the environment of IT professionals for **reporting wrongdoing related to software** in their workplace.

We define wrongdoing related to software as illegal or unethical behavior caused or happening within the software.

Examples of wrongdoing related to software are privacy and security issues, discrimination happening within the software (e.g., favoring certain users by an algorithm or allowing hate speech against specific user groups), enabling fraud or corruption, endangering someone's health and safety (e.g., motivating addictive behavior, triggering depressing thoughts), and damaging the environment (e.g., algorithms with too many CO2 emissions).

Your participation in this survey is completely voluntary and all of your responses will be treated anonymously, i.e., none of the responses will be connected to identifying information.

If you have any questions about this study, please contact me directly by sending an email to: s.reijenga@student.vu.nl

***Required**

1. Do you currently work as an IT professional? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

2. Which of the following options best describes your current IT role/position within your organization? *

Mark only one oval.

- Business Analyst
- Consultant
- Cyber Security Analyst
- Data Analyst
- Data Scientist
- Hardware Technician
- Helpdesk Support or Helpdesk Analyst
- IT Director or CIO
- IT Manager
- Network Engineer or Network Administrator
- Project Manager
- Product Owner
- Research Scientist
- Scrum Master
- Software Architect
- Software Engineer
- Software Tester
- Other: _____

Demographic Information

3. What is your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to answer
- Other: _____

4. What is your age? *

Mark only one oval.

- < 25 years old
- 25 - 35 years old
- 36 - 45 years old
- 46 - 55 years old
- 56 - 65 years old
- > 66 years old

5. What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed? *

Mark only one oval.

- No formal education
- High school
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate
- Other: _____

6. How long have you been working at your current organization? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0 - 2 years
- 3 - 5 years
- 6 - 10 years
- > 10 years

7. How long have you been working as an IT professional? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0 - 2 years
- 3 - 5 years
- 6 - 10 years
- 11 - 20 years
- > 20 years

8. What kind of industry is your organization part of? *

Mark only one oval.

- Education
- Financial services
- Industrial and Manufacturing services
- IT products and services
- Medical and Healthcare services
- Media and Creative Industry
- Public and Social services
- Retail and Distribution
- Other: _____

9. Do you work for a private or public organization? *

Mark only one oval.

Private organization

Public organization

10. What is the size of the organization you work in? *

Mark only one oval.

1 - 9 employees

10 - 100 employees

101 - 500 employees

501 - 1000 employees

1001 - 100.000 employees

> 100.000 employees

11. Which region is your organization based in? *

Mark only one oval.

Africa

Asia

Europe

Middle East

North America

Oceania

South America

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Enabling
and
obstructing
factors
when
reporting
wrongdoing
related to
software

Examples of wrongdoing related to software are privacy and security issues, discrimination happening within the software (e.g., favoring certain users by an algorithm or allowing hate speech against specific user groups), enabling fraud or corruption, endangering someone's health and safety (e.g., motivating addictive behavior, triggering depressing thoughts), and damaging the environment (e.g., algorithms with too many CO2 emissions).

12. As an IT professional which one of these actions do you think is the most effective way to stop wrongdoing related to software? (Choose only one) *

Mark only one oval.

- By directly confronting the wrongdoer
- By informally addressing the wrongdoing to coworkers or management (e.g., at the weekly status meeting or at the coffee machine)
- By formally reporting the wrongdoing within the organization via official channels (e.g., email, hotline, web-based system)
- By formally reporting the wrongdoing to a regulator outside the organization via official channels (e.g., email, hotline, web-based system)
- By reporting the wrongdoing to journalists or news organizations
- By reporting the wrongdoing directly to the general public, via the internet, Twitter, Facebook, or on online blogs
- None of the above – in my opinion, there is no effective way to stop wrongdoing
- Don't know
- Other: _____

13. As an IT professional which of the following factors would enable you to report wrongdoing related to software? (Choose all relevant answers) *

Tick all that apply.

- If I am guaranteed confidentiality (i.e., I share my name and know management or investigators would not share my identity with anyone)
- If I can report anonymously (i.e., my identity is not shared with anyone)
- If I know that I will be compensated for any harm I might suffer as a result of making my report
- If I know that it will make a difference to those affected by the wrongdoing
- If I know that my organization will act on my report
- If I receive a financial reward for making a report
- There are no enabling factors for me to report wrongdoing
- Other: _____

14. As an IT professional which of the following barriers would prevent you from reporting wrongdoing related to software? (Choose all relevant answers) *

Tick all that apply.

- Concern I could lose my job
- Concern for my future career prospects
- Concern that my report will make no difference
- Concern that colleagues could lose their jobs
- Concern I would be isolated by my colleagues
- Difficulty to prove the threat or harm
- Do not know how or where to report
- Fear of financial consequences
- Fear of legal consequences
- It would be an act of disloyalty
- Negative attitudes towards people reporting wrongdoing
- There are no barriers for me to report wrongdoing
- Other: _____

15. As an IT professional when do you think it is appropriate to report wrongdoing related to software to journalists, media, or an online platform? (Choose only one) *

Mark only one oval.

- As the first option in any situation
- Whenever there becomes a specific reason to do so
- Only as a last resort, if all else fails
- Never
- Don't know

16. I am familiar with legislation aiming to protect people that report wrongdoing related to software (whistleblowers) *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

Skip to question 17

Procedures
and
mechanisms

Examples of wrongdoing related to software are privacy and security issues, discrimination happening within the software (e.g., favoring certain users by an algorithm or allowing hate speech against specific user groups), enabling fraud or corruption, endangering someone's health and safety (e.g., motivating addictive behavior, triggering depressing thoughts), and damaging the environment (e.g., algorithms with too many CO2 emissions).

17. It is important that IT professionals speak up when witnessing wrongdoing related to software *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

18. It is in the interest of my organization for IT professionals to speak up about wrongdoing related to software *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

19. If I observed wrongdoing related to software in my workplace, I would feel personally obliged to report it to someone in my organization *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

20. If I reported wrongdoing related to software in my organization, I am confident something appropriate would be done about it *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

21. Management in my organization is serious about protecting people who report wrongdoing related to software *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

22. I am aware of the procedures/mechanisms to use when reporting wrongdoing related to software within my organization *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

23. Which of the following channels are available to employees in your organization to formally report wrongdoing related to software? (Choose all relevant answers) *

Tick all that apply.

- Internal hotline
- External hotline (outsourced to a third-party provider)
- Dedicated email
- In-person reporting
- Internal web-based system
- External web-based system (outsourced to a third-party provider)
- Don't know
- There are no formal channels available to report wrongdoing related to software
- Other: _____

24. Is it possible for employees in your organization to report wrongdoing related to software anonymously? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

25. I would be comfortable using the current procedures/mechanisms in place to formally report any wrongdoing related to software in my organization *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

26. What obstacles would prevent you from using the current reporting procedures/mechanisms in your organization? (Choose all relevant answers) *

Tick all that apply.

- I am not confident that the current procedures/mechanisms will resolve the issue
 Reporting may result in retaliation against me
 Process may not be anonymous (i.e., my identity would be shared)
 Process may not be confidential (i.e., I shared my name with management or investigators and they shared my identity with anyone else)
 Procedures/mechanisms are not clear to me
 No obstacles preventing me from using the current reporting mechanisms or procedures
 Other: _____

27. Have you ever witnessed or had suspicions that some form of wrongdoing related to software may have taken place within your current organization? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No Skip to question 32

Actions
based on
your
observations

Examples of wrongdoing related to software are privacy and security issues, discrimination happening within the software (e.g., favoring certain users by an algorithm or allowing hate speech against specific user groups), enabling fraud or corruption, endangering someone's health and safety (e.g., motivating addictive behavior, triggering depressing thoughts), and damaging the environment (e.g., algorithms with too many CO2 emissions).

28. In case you became aware of wrongdoing related to software in your workplace and you did not take action, what was the reason? (Choose all relevant answers) *

Tick all that apply.

- I decided the breach was not serious enough for me to report
- I did not know who to address or where to report
- I knew there would be no adequate response from my organization
- I think reporting wrongdoing is not right
- I wanted to protect the person who was committing the wrongdoing
- I was afraid of legal or financial consequences against myself
- I was afraid that my relationship with the management would be ruined
- Such violations are usual practice in the organization I am employed at
- The victim of the wrongdoing did not want me to report it
- I did take action
- Other: _____

29. If you became aware of wrongdoing related to software in your workplace and you did not take action, could you explain why you didn't?

30. In case you became aware of wrongdoing related to software in your workplace and you did take action, how did you act? (Choose all relevant answers) *

Tick all that apply.

- I informally addressed the wrongdoing to coworkers or management (e.g., at the weekly status meeting or at the coffee machine)
- I spoke directly to the person who committed the wrongdoing
- I reported formally within the organization via an official channel (e.g., email, hotline, web-based system)
- I reported formally to a regulator outside the organization via an official channel (e.g., email, hotline, web-based system)
- I reported to journalists or news organizations
- I reported directly to the general public, via the internet, Twitter, Facebook, or on online blogs
- I did not take action
- Other: _____

31. If you did take action, what was the reaction of your organization? *

Mark only one oval.

- The situation has been corrected
- The organization did nothing
- The action is still being processed
- The organization took action against me
- Not applicable
- Other: _____

32. Is there anything else you would like to share with us?

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